

Ergodic capacity computation in cognitive radio aided non-orthogonal multiple access systems

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the performance of cognitive radio system benefits from non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) scheme. We then examine system metrics to adjust its quality of signal processing. We focus on performance of the secondary network containing NOMA users which have some impacts from normal user and primary nodes. We refer to enhancement of the fairness and spectrum utilization by enabling spectrum sharing. In particular, the NOMA power allocation factors are assigned to provide different ergodic capacities for two NOMA users in the downlink of such cognitive radio-non-orthogonal multiple access (CR-NOMA) system. This article presents approximated ergodic capacity of secondary users, in which this system adopts the Rayleigh fading. The closed-form expressions are expected to match with Monte-Carlo simulation results and main system parameters can be determined to control performance of such CR-NOMA. Finally, this system is prominent once its performance outperforms than that of conventional orthogonal multiple access (OMA)-based system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

To enhance the spectrum efficiency, CR is a promising technique to allocate the secondary users to access the licensed spectrum dynamically [1]–[3]. The strategies of underlay and/or overlay spectrum sharing are widely deployed to benefit CR scheme to emerging networks. To avoid collision with the primary network (PN) in the overlay strategy, the secondary users detect the underutilized licensed spectrum to access the PN [4]–[6]. In case of the underlay strategy, the licensed spectrum can be shared with the secondary network by managing the interfere to the primary receivers under a threshold [7]–[9].

Besides CR technique, NOMA technique can further improve the spectrum efficiency [10]–[15]. In the context of NOMA [16]–[21], the transmitters allocate different transmit power levels to multiple users to access on the same frequency. The receiver employing successive interference cancellation (SIC) to distinguish the different signals [22]. Thanks to benefits of both the CR and NOMA techniques, the CR-NOMA networks will not only increase the number of serving users and enhance the spectrum efficiency as well, which is a promising system for the 5th generation wireless networks [23]. Li *et al.* the authors [24] designed the relaying scheme employed in the secondary network of the considered CR-NOMA. In such, a relay is allowed to wireless power transfer to far users in the secondary network. Mu *et al.* in [25], by combining NOMA and CR network, such system provides to users a new era of reliable, seamless, and massive connectivity. In particular, this work studied the relay selection in CR-NOMA networks to achieve advantage of the spectrum sharing model.

The missing analysis in recent results in [24], [25] has motivated to consider ergodic capacity of CR-NOMA system.

The remaining parts of this article is summarized is being as. We describe scheme of CR-NOMA for signal processing at secondary users in section 2. We compute expressions of signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR). The closed-form formula of ergodic capacity is presented in section 3 and then main simulation results are verified in section 4. In section 5, we provide some key findings to conclude the article.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

A CR-aided NOMA system is more important to examine its performance at secondary network (SN) in a downlink, as shown in Figure 1. Such SN includes of a secondary source (for example access point (AP)), two destination users (U_1, U_2), other cellular user equipment (CUE) as well as a primary destination (PD). The wireless channels in such CR-NOMA are adopted quasi-static independent but not identically distributed (i.i.n.d) Rayleigh fading. The links $AP \rightarrow PD$, $AP \rightarrow U_1$, $AP \rightarrow U_2$, $CUE \rightarrow U_1$ and $CUE \rightarrow U_2$ experience with coefficients as $h_{SP} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_{SP})$, $h_{AU_1} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_{AU_1})$, $h_{AU_2} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_{AU_2})$, $h_{CU_1} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_{CU_1})$ and $h_{CU_2} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_{CU_2})$, respectively.

Figure 1. A sketch of of CR-aided NOMA system

In the considered system, the cognitive transmitter intends to send signals to the secondary destinations. To guarantee operation of primary network, the secondary source AP keeps the transmit power as the following constraint [26]:

$$P_{AP} = \min \left(\bar{P}_{AP}, \frac{Q}{|h_{SP}|^2} \right), \tag{1}$$

in which the secondary transmitter has \bar{P}_{AP} as the maximum power. Of course, the transmit system is constrained by the interference at the primary receiver which is associated with threshold power of Q .

We call x_1, x_2 and x_{CUE} as the signals for U_1, U_2 and CUE , respectively. In NOMA, power allocation factors are a_1, a_2 , and $a_1 < a_2, a_1 + a_2 = 1$. The received signals at the two users are given by:

$$y_{U_i} = h_{AU_i} \left[\sum_{j=1}^2 \sqrt{a_j P_{AP}} x_j \right] + \sqrt{\kappa P_{CUE}} h_{CU_i} x_{CUE} + n_{U_i}, \quad i \in \{1, 2\}, \tag{2}$$

where $\kappa, 0 \leq \kappa \leq 1$ represents for scaling factor related to interference, n_{U_i} is additive white Gaussian noise with mean power N_0 , P_{AP} and P_{CUE} are the normalized transmission powers at the AP and CUE, respectively. h_{CU_i} is interference channel from the CUE to the users U_i and .

To further evaluate system performance, the SINR at user U_1 needs be computed. SINR at user U_1

treats signal from U_2 as noise, we have:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2 \rightarrow U_1} = \frac{\rho_{AP} a_2 |h_{AU_1}|^2}{a_1 \rho_{AP} |h_{AU_1}|^2 + \kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_1}|^2 + 1}, \quad (3)$$

where $\rho_{AP} = \frac{P_{AP}}{N_0}$ and $\rho_{CUE} = \frac{P_{CUE}}{N_0}$ are the transmit SNR at the AP and the CUE respectively.

By enabling SIC, we compute the SINR at U_1 by:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_1} = \frac{a_1 \rho_{AP} |h_{AU_1}|^2}{\kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_1}|^2 + 1}. \quad (4)$$

To detect its own signal x_2 , SINR at U_2 is given by:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2} = \frac{\rho_{AP} a_2 |h_{AU_2}|^2}{a_1 \rho_{AP} |h_{AU_2}|^2 + \kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_2}|^2 + 1}. \quad (5)$$

3. COMPUTATION OF ERGODIC CAPACITY

3.1. Ergodic capacity of U_1

By definition, we achieve ergodic capacity for user U_1 as:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{U_1} &= \frac{1}{2} E \{ \log(1 + \tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}) \} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} E \left\{ \log \left(1 + \underbrace{\frac{a_1 \rho_{AP} |h_{AU_1}|^2}{\kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_1}|^2 + 1}}_X \right) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1 - F_X(x)}{1+x} dx. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

It is noted that $F_X(x)$ is written by:

$$\begin{aligned} F_X(x) &= 1 - \Pr \left(|h_{AU_1}|^2 > \frac{x}{a_1 \bar{\rho}_{AP}} (\kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_1}|^2 + 1), |h_{SP}|^2 < \frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} \right) \\ &\quad - \Pr \left(|h_{AU_1}|^2 > \frac{x}{a_1 \rho_Q} (\kappa \rho_{CUE} |h_{CU_1}|^2 |h_{SP}|^2 + |h_{SP}|^2), |h_{SP}|^2 > \frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} \right) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^{\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}}} f_{|h_{SP}|^2}(y) \int_0^\infty f_{|h_{CU_1}|^2}(z) \left[1 - F_{|h_{AU_1}|^2} \left(\frac{x (\kappa \rho_{CUE} z + 1)}{a_1 \bar{\rho}_{AP}} \right) \right] dy dz \\ &\quad - \int_{\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}^\infty f_{|h_{SP}|^2}(y) \int_0^\infty f_{|h_{CU_1}|^2}(z) \left[1 - F_{|h_{AU_1}|^2} \left(\frac{x (\kappa \rho_{CUE} z y + y)}{a_1 \rho_Q} \right) \right] dy dz \\ &= 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}} \right) \frac{e^{-\frac{x}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{\lambda_{CU_1}} \int_0^\infty e^{-z \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{CU_1}} + \frac{\kappa \rho_{CUE} x}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}} \right)} dz \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\lambda_{SP} \lambda_{CU_1}} \int_{\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}^\infty e^{-y \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q} \right)} \int_0^\infty e^{-z \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{CU_1}} + \frac{\kappa \rho_{CUE} y x}{\eta \rho_Q} \right)} dy dz \\ &= 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}} \right) \frac{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} e^{-\frac{x}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{(\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} + \nu x)} - \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP} \nu x} \int_{\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}^\infty \frac{e^{-y \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q} \right)}}{\left[\frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu x} + y \right]} dy, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\eta = \lambda_{AU_1} a_1$ and $\nu = \lambda_{CU_1} \kappa \rho_{CUE}$.

We using [[27], (3.352.2)] $F_X(x)$ is given as:

$$F_X(x) = 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}}\right) \frac{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} e^{-\frac{x}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{[\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} + \nu x]} + \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP} \nu x} e^{\frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu x} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q}\right)} Ei \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu x} \right) \right). \tag{8}$$

Substituting (8) into (6), C_{U_1} is given as:

$$C_{U_1} = \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \int_0^{\frac{a_2}{a_1}} \frac{1}{1+x} (1 - F_X(x)) dx = \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{1+x} \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}}\right) \frac{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} e^{-\frac{x}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{(\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} + \nu x)} - \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP} \nu x} e^{\frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu x} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q}\right)} Ei \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\eta \rho_Q} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu x} \right) \right) \right] dx. \tag{9}$$

Let $t = \frac{4}{\pi} \arctan(x) - 1 \Rightarrow \tan\left(\frac{\pi(t+1)}{4}\right) = x \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4} \sec^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4}(t+1)\right) dt = dx$, C_{U_1} is given by:

$$C_{U_1} = \frac{\pi}{8 \ln 2} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sec^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4}(t+1)\right)}{1 + \ell(t)} \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}}\right) \frac{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} e^{-\frac{\ell(t)}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{(\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} + \nu \ell(t))} - \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP} \nu \ell(t)} e^{\frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu \ell(t)} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\ell(t)}{\eta \rho_Q}\right)} Ei \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\ell(t)}{\eta \rho_Q} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu \ell(t)} \right) \right) \right] dt. \tag{10}$$

where $\ell(t) = \tan\left(\frac{\pi(t+1)}{4}\right)$.

Unfortunately, deriving a closed-form expression for (10) is difficult task, we can obtain accurate approximation. We have new result using Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature [[28] (25.4.38)].

$$C_{U_1} \approx \frac{\pi^2}{8T \ln 2} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\sqrt{1 - \varphi_t^2}}{1 + \ell(\varphi_t)} \sec^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4}(\varphi_t + 1)\right) \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP} \lambda_{SP}}}\right) \frac{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} e^{-\frac{\ell(\varphi_t)}{\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP}}}}{(\eta \bar{\rho}_{AP} + \nu \ell(\varphi_t))} - \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP} \nu \ell(\varphi_t)} e^{\frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu \ell(\varphi_t)} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\ell(\varphi_t)}{\eta \rho_Q}\right)} Ei \left(- \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\ell(\varphi_t)}{\eta \rho_Q} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \frac{\eta \rho_Q}{\nu \ell(\varphi_t)} \right) \right) \right], \tag{11}$$

where $\varphi_t = \cos\left(\frac{2t-1}{2T} \pi\right)$.

3.2. Ergodic capacity of U_2

Similarly as computation for U_1 , the ergodic capacity for U_2 is formulated by:

$$C_{U_2} = \frac{1}{2} E \{ \log(1 + \tilde{\gamma}_{U_2}) \} = \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \int_0^{\frac{a_2}{a_1}} \frac{1}{1+x} \bar{F}_{|h_{AU_2}|^2} \left(\frac{x}{a_2 - a_1 x} \right) dx, \tag{12}$$

in which $\bar{F}_{|h_{AU_2}|^2}(x) = 1 - F_{|h_{AU_2}|^2}(x)$ denotes the complementary CDF of $|h_{AU_2}|^2$. We continue to have $F_{|h_{AU_2}|^2}(x)$ which is similar as (8).

$$F_{|h_{AU_2}|^2}(x) = \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP}\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}\right) \frac{\lambda_{AU_2} e^{-\frac{x}{\lambda_{AU_2}\bar{\rho}_{AP}[a_2-a_1x]}}}{\left(\lambda_{AU_2} + \lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\frac{\rho_{CUE}x}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}[a_2-a_1x]}\right)} + \frac{\rho_Q[a_2-a_1x]\lambda_{AU_2}}{\lambda_{SP}\lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}x} e^{\frac{\rho_Q[a_2-a_1x]\lambda_{AU_2}}{\lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}x}} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\rho_Q\lambda_{AU_2}[a_2-a_1x]}\right) \times Ei\left(-\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{x}{\rho_Q\lambda_{AU_2}[a_2-a_1x]}\right)\left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \frac{\rho_Q[a_2-a_1x]\lambda_{AU_2}}{\lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}x}\right)\right) \right]. \quad (13)$$

Substituting (13) into (12), C_{U_2} is calculated as:

$$C_{U_2} = \frac{1}{2\ln 2} \int_0^{\frac{a_2}{a_1}} \frac{1}{1+x} \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP}\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}\right) \frac{\lambda_{AU_2} e^{-\frac{\bar{\delta}_{AP}(x)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}}}{\left(\lambda_{AU_2} + \lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}\bar{\delta}_{AP}(x)\right)} - \frac{\vartheta(x)}{\lambda_{SP}} e^{\vartheta(x)\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\bar{\delta}_{Q}(x)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}\right)} Ei\left(-\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\bar{\delta}_{Q}(x)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}\right)\left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \vartheta(x)\right)\right) \right] dx, \quad (14)$$

where $\bar{\delta}_{AP}(x) = \frac{x}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}[a_2-a_1x]}$, $\bar{\delta}_{Q}(x) = \frac{x}{\rho_Q[a_2-a_1x]}$ and $\vartheta(x) = \frac{\lambda_{AU_2}}{\lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}\bar{\delta}_{Q}(x)}$.

Although, achieving a closed-form expression for (14) is tough task, an accurate approximation could be considered by employing Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature [[27] (25.4.38)], C_{U_2} is given by:

$$C_{U_2} \approx \frac{\pi a_2}{2K \ln 2} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\sqrt{1-\phi_k^2}}{2a_1 + a_2(\phi_k + 1)} \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho_Q}{\lambda_{SP}\bar{\rho}_{AP}}}\right) \frac{\lambda_{AU_2} e^{-\frac{\Delta(\phi_k)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}}}{\left(\lambda_{AU_2} + \lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}\Delta(\phi_k)\right)} - \frac{\vartheta(\phi_k)}{\lambda_{SP}} e^{\vartheta(\phi_k)\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\Theta(\phi_k)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}\right)} Ei\left(-\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{SP}} + \frac{\Theta(\phi_k)}{\lambda_{AU_2}}\right)\left(\frac{\rho_Q}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}} + \vartheta(\phi_k)\right)\right) \right], \quad (15)$$

where $\phi_k = \cos\left(\frac{2k-1}{2K}\pi\right)$, $\Delta(x) = \frac{a_2(t+1)}{\bar{\rho}_{AP}a_1[a_2(1-t)]}$, $\Theta(x) = \frac{a_2(t+1)}{\rho_Q a_1[a_2(1-t)]}$ and $\vartheta(x) = \frac{\lambda_{AU_2}}{\lambda_{CU_2}\kappa\rho_{CUE}\Theta(x)}$.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To verify closed-form expressions, we set power factor $a_2 = 0.9$. The wireless channels are characterized as $\lambda_{SP} = d_0^{-\beta}$, $\lambda_{AU_1} = d_1^{-\beta}$, $\lambda_{AU_2} = (1 - U_1)^{-\beta}$, $\lambda_{CU_1} = d_{CU_1}^{-\beta}$ and $\lambda_{CU_2} = d_{CU_2}^{-\beta}$, along with distances are $d_0 = 0.1$, $d_1 = 0.3$, $d_{CU_1} = 0.3$ and $d_{CU_2} = 0.7$, path-loss exponent is $\beta = 2$. Although depending on service required, data rates should be $R_1 = 1$ and $R_2 = 0.5$. We set SNR of interference from primary network $\rho_Q = 30$ dB. To obtain a close approximation, the Gauss-Chebyshev parameter could be $T = K = 20$.

Figures 2-4 exhibit ergodic capacity for considered CR-NOMA. We can see the trend of curves in term of ergodic capacity with different values of κ for Figure 2. Especially in Figure 3, at fixed value of ρ_Q , the ergodic capacity only increase at lower range of ρ_Q , after the point $\rho_Q = 35$, the ergodic capacity keeps unchanged.

In Figure 3, higher power of interference from the CUE is main reason to make ergodic capacity of two users reduce. It can be seen ergodic capacity of two users are low at high region of κ . Figure 5 confirms that CR system relying NOMA outperforms than that using OMA scheme.

Figure 2. Ergodic capacity versus transmit SNR at the RSU

Figure 3. Ergodic capacity versus transmit SNR at the primary node, with $\kappa = 0.1$

Figure 4. Ergodic capacity versus κ , with $\bar{\rho}_{RSU} = 30$ [dB]

Figure 5. Comparison between CR scheme with OMA and with NOMA, with $\kappa = 0.1$ and $\rho_Q = 30$ [dB]

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have evaluated performance of underlay CR-NOMA network by introducing the closed-form expressions of ergodic capacity under Rayleigh fading. We can confirm exactness of the derived closed-form expressions by numerical results, and the ergodic capacity of CR-NOMA and CR-OMA were compared. The proposed CR-NOMA can improve ergodic capacity at high region of transmit SNR at the secondary source. Moreover, the numerical results showed that the different power allocation factors lead to performance gap among two users and the performance fairness is achieved for both users.

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